

PRODUCTION AND EVALUATION OF PROTEIN QUALITY OF BREAD FROM WHEAT / COWPEA FLOUR BLENDS.

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ABSTRACT

The protein quality of bread samples produced from wheat and cowpea flour blends was investigated. The wheat flour (WF) was composite with cowpea flour (CF) at the levels of 10%, 20%, 30% and 40% and used for bread production. The samples of bread produced were later sliced, dried and milled systematically into bread flours. The resulting bread flours were individually formulated into test diets whereas the casein based diet was similarly formulated and used as control. After formulation, the protein quality of the test diets and the control were evaluated using the protein efficiency ratio index with thirty-five weanling albino rats. The rats which were six weeks old and weighing between 42.3 and 44.1 grammas were divided into five groups of seven rats each and housed in individual metabolic cages; fed diets and tap water adlibitum for a period of 21 days. From the results, the corrected protein efficiency ratio (PER) of casein based diet was 2.5 and those of the test diets formulated from bread were 2.18, 2.23, 2.30 and 2.32 respectively. However, the values of the correct protein efficiency ratio of the bread formulated diets were generally lower than that of the casein based diet irrespective of the level of fortification of the bread samples with cowpea flour.

KEYWORDS: Bread, production, protein quality evaluation, wheat - cowpea flour blends.

INTRODUCTION

Bread is a flour confection that may be regarded as a solid foam with a multitude of pockets of carbon dioxide distributed uniformly throughout its bulk. Bread is basically a yeast-raised bakery product that has a honey comb structure. The consumption of bread and other baked goods such as biscuits, doughnuts and cakes produced from wheat flour has become very popular in Nigeria and most developing nations of the tropics especially among children Banigo and Edward, (1977). The low protein content of wheat flour, which is the most vital ingredient used for the production of different kinds of baked goods has been of major concern in its utilization. The enrichment of bread and other cereal based confections with legume flours particularly in regions where protein utilization is inadequate has long been recognized. This is because legume proteins are high in lysine, an essential limiting amino acid in most cereals (Mcwatters and Brantley, 1982). Legumes generally contain relatively high amount of protein compared to other plant foodstuffs. Legumes can therefore complement cereals only when blended at optimum ratio.

Cowpea, (*Vigna unguiculata*) a grain legume, is one of the richest and inexpensive sources of plant protein that can be used to improve the diet of individuals especially the poor and low income earners in both developed and developing countries of the world because of its high protein content (Enwere, 1998). Of the legumes consumed in Nigeria, cowpea appears to be the most popular because it can easily be utilized in many food preparations. Cowpea can be processed into paste, flour, protein isolates and concentrates which can be used for the preparation of various food products (Okaka and Potter, 1979; Ngoddy *et al*, 1986; Enwere and Ebiogwu, 1993). Generally, cowpea is unique as a food ingredient because it can be prepared into different foods prior to consumption. The seedling, tender green leaves, and seeds and pods that are fresh and immature can be cooked and eaten as vegetable.

When dry and mature, it can be cooked as dehulled and undehulled seeds and eaten as soups, stews and with vegetables, fruits, maize, plantains, rice, cassava and other foods. Cowpea is one of the well known and utilized sources of plant protein, which when used partially to replace or substitute wheat flour in the preparation of bread and other flour confectionery would help to improve their protein content and nutritional quality. The objective of this study was to evaluate the protein quality of bread samples produced from wheat/cowpea flour blends at different levels of substitution.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The wheat flour and brown variety of cowpea seeds (*Vigna unguiculata*) used for this study were bought from a local market in Enugu. This research work was carried out in the Department of Food Science and Technology, Enugu, State University of Science and Technology, Enugu, Nigeria in August, 2002.

Preparation of Cowpea Flour

The cowpea flour was prepared according to the method described by Okaka (1997) as shown in Figure 1. During preparation, two kilograms of cowpea seeds which were free from dirt and other contaminating materials such as stones, sticks and leaves were weighed, cleaned and soaked in potable water for 2h. Thereafter, the seeds were drained, dehulled manually, boiled (100°C, 30min) and dried in the tray dryer (65°C, 6h). During drying, the dehulled seeds were stirred at intervals of 20 minutes to ensure uniform drying. The dried seeds were milled (attrition mill) and sieved to pass through a 400µm mesh sieve. The cooked cowpea flour produced was finally vacuum packaged in polyethylene bags for blending and production of bread.

Flour Blending

The wheat flour (WF) was composite with cowpea flour (CF) at the levels of 10%, 20%, 30% and 40% in a Kenwood mixer (Model A 220). Thereafter, the flour blends were individually vacuum packaged in polyethylene bags and kept at ambient temperature conditions until used for the production of bread.

Preparation of Bread

The bread samples were prepared according to the traditional straight dough development method described by Ihekoronye (1999) as shown in Figure 2. The basic formulation was 100% flour, 60% fat, 40% sucrose, 20% water, 10% salt and 5% yeast. The 100% flour was thoroughly replaced for wheat flour (WF) with 10%, 20%, 30% and 40% cowpea flour (CF). During the bread making, the ingredients with the exception of the yeast were mixed together in a mixer (Model A 220) to form hard consistent dough. Thereafter, the yeast was activated by putting the yeast in a small plastic container containing little quantity of warm water, sugar (sucrose) and flour and the container was then covered and kept at room temperature until the yeast was fully activated. After the activation of the yeast, the bread dough obtained was pierced at the centre and the activated yeast solution was carefully poured to the centre of the hole. The bread dough containing the yeast was continuously kneaded manually in a plastic bowl until the gluten protein of the dough was properly developed. Thereafter, the kneaded dough was covered properly and allowed to ferment at ambient temperature condition for 3h. After fermentation, the dough was repeatedly punched or knocked back until the gluten protein of the dough attained its maximum extensibility and elasticity. When the knocking back process was over, the knocked back dough was again covered and allowed to ferment for another 2h. After that, the punched and fermented dough was further knocked back, divided and moulded into uniform shapes of similar sizes. The divided and moulded bread dough pieces were placed into individual greased baking pans and proofed in a hot air rotatory oven (45°C, 30min). Thereafter, the proofed bread dough pieces were finally baked in a hot air oven (200°C, 50min). The bread loaves produced were cooled immediately after baking, depanned and packaged individually in sealed polyethylene bags and kept in refrigerated conditions until used for the formulation of the test diets. The various samples of bread produced from wheat/cowpea flour blends are shown in Table 1.

Formulation of Test Diets

The diets were formulated according to the method described by Obizoba (1996). Prior to the formulation of the diets, the bread loaves produced and kept in refrigerated conditions were individually sliced into smaller sizes and then dried further in the tray dryer (60°C, 1h). Thereafter, the dried bread slices were consequently milled (attrition mill) into bread flours. After milling, the protein content of the bread flours was determined according to the modified micro-kjeldahl method described by AOAC (1995) before being used for the formulation of test diets. Based on the values of the protein content of the bread flours used for the formulation of the test diets, the total amounts in grammes, for each diet was calculated. The diets were formulated to provide 10 percent protein regardless of the nitrogen sources (Okaka *et al*; 1992). During the formulation, calculated quantity of sugar (sucrose) and cornstarch were added only to the casein based diet used as control or reference protein diet whereas no additional corn starch and sugar were added to the bread containing diets.

This was because the bread containing diets contributed enough quantity of sugar and starch to the products. Other nutrients such as mineral mix, vegetable oil and vitamin mix were also added to each of the diet to balance the diets. Generally, 1.2 kilogrammes of each diet was thoroughly formulated for the purpose of the nutritional study. Thereafter, the formulated diets were individually packaged in air tight containers and kept in refrigerated conditions until used for the nutritional study with rats. The proportions of the ingredients used for the formulation of the test

diets based on their protein contents and those used for the formulation of 1.2 kilogrammes of each diet used for the nutritional study are shown in Tables 2 and 3.

Nutritional Study with Rats

The nutritional study was performed with thirty-five weanling albino rats (*Munsorvegicus albinus*). The albino rats were obtained from the Animal Science Unit, University of Nigeria Teaching Hospital, Enugu and the rats generally were six weeks old, weighing between 42.3 and 44.1 grammes. The rats were divided into five groups of seven rats each and housed in individual metabolic cages; fed diets and tap water ad libitum for a period of 21 days. The cages were made of stainless steel and were equipped with screen - bottom to separate urine and faeces of the animals. The nutritional study was carried out according to the procedure described by Lister and McCance (1998). Prior to the study, the rats were weighed initially to assess the test diets and at the end of the study to determine any change in initial body weight. During the nutritional study with the rats, 50 grammes of each of the test diets was weighed out and fed into individual feeding troughs placed into each metabolic cages where the albino rats were individually housed. The rats were provided with tap water with the aid of the plastic drinkers mounted on individual metabolic cages.

The rats were fed on the diets and tap water for a period of 21 days. Also, the amount of each diet consumed by each group of the rat was monitored per day throughout the period of the study. This was accomplished by weighing individually the left over diet found in individual feeding troughs after careful collection every morning until the study was over. In the same vein, the rats in turn were weighed at intervals of 3 days to determine the rate of change in their body weight. After the study, the protein quality of the test diets was evaluated using the protein efficiency ratio index as stated below:

$$\text{Protein efficiency ratio (PER)} = \frac{\text{increase in weight of the rats}}{\text{weight of protein consumed}}$$

Thereafter, the results of the protein efficiency ratio of the test diets obtained after evaluation were converted to their corresponding values of corrected protein efficiency ratio according to the method of Obizota (1996) as indicated below:

$$\text{Corrected protein efficiency ratio (CPER)} = \frac{\text{PER of the test Protein}}{\text{PER of casein}} \times 2.5$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the protein efficiency ratio of the test diets are shown in Table 4. From the results, the protein efficiency ratio index of the diets showed that with a casein corrected protein efficiency ratio of 2.5, those for the bread formulated test diets had the corrected protein efficiency ratio ranging from 2.18 to 2.32. The decrease in the values of the protein efficiency ratio of the bread based diets could be due to the effect of maillard browning or carbonyl-amine reaction which occur between hydrolysed sucrose component and free amino groups of basic amino acids notably lysine and methionine which are dietary essential to various laboratory animals including man. However, this reaction has been incriminated in decreased protein activity in albino rats (Finot, 1982; Struthers *et al*; 1983; Lindly, 1987). Generally, the values of the protein efficiency ratio of the bread containing diets increased steadily with increasing content of cowpea flour.

CONCLUSION

Bread samples of appreciable protein content and quality were produced from wheat/cowpea flour blends. From the findings of this study, it was observed that the protein efficiency ratio (PER) scores of the bread formulated diets increased steadily with increasing supplementation with cowpea flour. The enrichment of bread with the addition of adequately processed cowpea flour, would help to improve their protein content and quality. Further studies should be performed on wheat/cowpea flour blended samples of bread to determine their respective shelf life and amino acid profile.

Fig 1: Flow chart for the production of cooked cowpea flour.

Fig 2: Flow chart for bread production.

Table 1: Samples of Bread

Samples	WF (%)	CF (%)
A	90	10
B	80	20
C	70	30
D	60	40

Key:

- A – Bread made with 90% wheat flour and 10% cowpea flour.
- B – Bread made with 80% wheat flour and 20% cowpea flour
- C – Bread made with 70% wheat flour and 30% cowpea flour
- D – Bread made with 60% wheat flour and 40% cowpea flour

Table 2: Composition of The Diet Based on Their percent Protein contents.

	Diet Group				
Ingredients	I	II	III	IV	V
Casein	10.42	-	-	-	-
Bread	-	89.16	91.68	93.43	93.73
Vegetable oil	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
Vitamin mix	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Mineral mix	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
Sucrose	4.5	-	-	-	-
Corn starch	80.08	-	-	-	-

Key:

- I – Casein based diet used as control or references protein
- II – Diet formulated from bread made with 90% wheat flour and 10% cowpea flour.
- III – Diet formulated from bread made with 80% wheat flour and 20% cowpea flour.
- IV – Diet formulated from bread made with 70% wheat flour and 30% cowpea flour.
- V – Diet formulated from bread made with 60% wheat flour and 40% cowpea flour.

Table 3: Composition of 1.2kg of The Test Diet Used for The Nutritional Study.

	Diet Group				
Ingredients	I	II	III	IV	V
Casein	144.04	-	-	-	-
Bread	-	1112.6	1114.8	1116.38	1116.61
Vegetable oil	30	31.20	30.20	29.87	29.87
Vitamin mix	18	18.72	18.24	17.92	17.87
Mineral mix	36	34.44	36.48	35.85	35.94
Sucrose	54	-	-	-	-
Corn starch	960.96	-	-	-	-

The proportions of ingredients are as shown in Table 2.

Table 4: Protein Efficiency Ratio of Test Diets.

	Diet Group				
Parameter	I	II	III	IV	V
Protein efficiency ratio (PER)	0.8940	0.7152	0.7900	0.8155	0.8168
Correction protein efficiency ratio (PER)	2.5	2.18	2.23	2.30	2.32

Key:

- I – Casein based diet used as control or references protein
- II – Diet formulated from bread made with 90% wheat flour and 10% cowpea flour.
- III – Diet formulated from bread made with 80% wheat flour and 20% cowpea flour.
- IV – Diet formulated from bread made with 70% wheat flour and 30% cowpea flour.
- V – Diet formulated from bread made with 60% wheat flour and 40% cowpea flour.

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